

JALON

**Regional Energy Community Project
Design**

Trentino – Alto Adige / Italy

Project Title	Regional Energy Community Project Design in Italy
Version	V0.1
Date	03/02/2026
Authors	Eurac Research

Content

<i>1. Context</i>	4
<i>2. Scope of the project design</i>	4
<i>3. Characterization of the region</i>	5
<i>4. Sizing of PV systems</i>	13
<i>5. Financial model</i>	14
<i>6. Business plan</i>	14
<i>7. Legal aspects</i>	18
<i>8. Methodology for engagement</i>	20
<i>9. Conclusions</i>	21

1. Context

EURAC, as the entity responsible for the design of ECs in Trentino – Alto Adige, participated in the Calatayud experience to acquire operational and methodological knowledge. In parallel, it conducted an in-depth analysis of the regional context, in order to identify constraints and specific territorial characteristics, enabling a targeted adaptation of the practices and lessons learned.

EURAC was able to identify the main challenges and the key changes needed in Italy to establish a supportive local framework that would enable the replication of the Calatayud experience. This was made possible by being kept fully informed at every stage of the project: from participatory processes to identify early adopters, to local training through workshops, to communication and dissemination activities, to regulatory analysis aimed at identifying barriers and strategies for adapting energy community (EC) legislation to rural areas, as well as the exploration of financing models, including public grants.

2. Scope of the project design

JALON aims to develop an innovative approach to facilitate the establishment, growth, and long-term sustainability of ECs, which are designed to address specific social needs of citizens. The project employs a methodology based on close collaboration among local stakeholders. Its focus is primarily on rural areas, where significant obstacles, complex territorial conditions, and particular needs often hinder the pace of the energy transition. Across Europe, numerous factors limit the full potential of ECs, with rural areas facing the greatest challenges. In Trentino Alto-Adige, these difficulties similarly act as barriers, which this project seeks to overcome.

Trentino Alto-Adige faces several structural challenges that affect rural development and quality of life. Mountainous and marginal areas suffer from limited accessibility, scarcity of services and non-essential goods, increasing depopulation, and difficulties in retaining young people and local labour. Agricultural businesses, often small and family-run, face high costs, low profitability, dependence on monocultures, and challenges in technological innovation and sustainable land management. At the same time, tourism, while a key economic driver, generates environmental pressure, congestion, and strong seasonality in energy demand, complicating resource management.

In this context, ECs can play a strategic role: by promoting the local production and sharing of renewable energy, they can reduce energy costs for households and rural businesses, stimulate innovation and autonomy in agriculture, encourage population retention in mountainous and marginal areas, and help balance seasonal peaks in energy demand related to tourism. In short, ECs represent a practical tool to integrate environmental sustainability, economic development, and social cohesion, thereby strengthening the overall resilience of the territory.

Within this project, a specific case study is first identified, serving as the reference point for analysis and experimentation. The energy consumption of the selected site is

carefully characterized to gain a detailed understanding of actual needs and electricity demand patterns. Based on this analysis, photovoltaic generation systems solutions are designed to meet the energy demand within a framework of sharing and cooperation within the energy community.

In parallel, the project develops a financial model and a business plan, essential tools to assess the economic feasibility of the initiative, ensure long-term sustainability, and attract potential investors or partners. Furthermore, the most appropriate legal form for the establishment of the Energy Community is analyzed and defined, providing a clear regulatory framework aligned with strategic and operational objectives.

Finally, particular attention is given to the social and participatory dimension: a methodology is designed to actively engage the local population and raise awareness of the environmental, economic, and social benefits of the energy transition.

3. *Characterization of the region*

The Trentino - Alto Adige region consists of two different autonomous provinces: the province of Bolzano, also known as Alto Adige and the province of Trento, also known as Trentino.

Alto Adige is located in the northern part of the Alpine arc, bordering Austria and Switzerland, and the province covers an area of nearly 7,400 km². Approximately 25% of this area is designated as protected land, including the Dolomites, which were recognized as a UNESCO Natural World Heritage Site in 2009¹. The region's geography is dominated by mountains and valleys, resulting in relatively low population density. As of January 1, 2025, Alto Adige had a population of about 539,000 inhabitants, with an average density of around 73 inhabitants per km². However, population distribution across the 118 municipalities of the province is uneven² and since the 1990s, Alto Adige has seen a marked increase in migration, both from other parts of Italy and from abroad².

Trentino is located in the central Alpine region and administratively, consists of 166 municipalities, organized into 15 valley communities. The province covers approximately 6,214 km². The terrain is predominantly mountainous, which leads to a very uneven distribution of the population across valleys and high-altitude areas. As of January 1, 2025, Trentino had about 546,709 inhabitants³, giving an average population density of 88 people per km².

Figure 1 illustrates the population distribution, and Figure 2, shows the population density across the municipalities of Trentino Alto-Adige.

¹ [The South Tyrolean Observatory for Sustainable Tourism](#)

² [Cavrini, G., & Lallo, C. Il contesto sociale e demografico in Alto Adige.](#)

³ [Institute of Statistics of the Autonomous Province of Trento - ISPAT](#)

Figure 1: Population distribution in the province of Bolzano (upper map) and in the province of Trento (lower map). Source ASTAT

Figure 2: Population density by municipality in the region Trentino - Alto Adige. Source ASTAT

Social and economic issues in rural areas

The Economic Research Institute (IRE) of the Bolzano Chamber of Commerce classifies municipalities with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants as "rural" zones⁴. However, these rural

⁴ [Economic Research Institute \(IRE\), Bolzano Chamber of Commerce, The Appeal of Rural Areas in South Tyrol \(Bolzano, 2021\)](#)

areas differ significantly in terms of economic structure, productive capacity, and geographical location, particularly due to their peripheral nature.

Among Autonomous Province of Bolzano's strategic objectives, as outlined in the Provincial Complement for Rural Development of the National Strategic Plan 2023 - 2027⁵, is the revitalization of rural areas. The province is committed to enhancing the economic, environmental, and social sustainability of these areas by promoting policies and tools that strengthen both their productive and social fabric.

These objectives are also shared by the Autonomous Province of Trento and are reflected in the Provincial Complement for Rural Development of the National Strategic Plan 2023 - 2027 for Trentino⁶.

Economically, it is essential to make the sector attractive to younger generations and competitive relative to other provincial activities. Sustainable agricultural practices are crucial, as environmentally responsible farming generates both direct and indirect economic value while creating complementary opportunities for other local enterprises. Despite their relatively low population density, rural areas play a strategic role: they retain residents who might otherwise migrate to cities, support the tourism sector, and enhance the region's landscape and natural heritage.

JALON aligns with the provincial plan's goals of fostering the economic and social development of rural areas. To this end, the provinces plan interventions to mitigate and adapt to climate change, develop sustainable energy, and encourage the production and use of renewable sources, thereby promoting the creation and expansion of ECs. Additionally, regional policies aim to attract young farmers, stimulate entrepreneurial activity, and promote employment, social inclusion, and local development in rural areas.

Rural areas, while offering significant advantages such as natural beauty, landscapes, favourable climate, and a high quality of life, also face persistent challenges. Limited accessibility and a scarcity of non-essential goods—often either in short supply or prohibitively expensive—constrain both economic and social development. Each year, Alto-Adige experiences a positive migration balance, with more people moving into the region than leaving it. However, most newcomers settle in cities and central areas, drawn by the availability of services and economic opportunities, leaving marginal Alpine valleys particularly vulnerable to depopulation.

Alongside the vulnerabilities of the agricultural sector and demographic and accessibility challenges, the strong tourism and commercial vocation of the territory must be considered. The natural and cultural conditions of Trentino – Alto Adige create significant opportunities for tourism, which could be developed sustainably to strengthen employment, growth, and social inclusion, particularly in the more marginal Alpine valleys at risk of depopulation. In these areas, integrated local development strategies and inter-territorial cooperation, built with the direct involvement of local communities, are crucial.

Over the past fifteen years, tourism has grown far beyond the resident population, with areas such as Val Gardena and Alta Badia reaching or even exceeding their hosting

⁵ [Provincia autonoma di Bolzano, Piano Strategico nazionale della PAC 2023-2027](#)

⁶ [Provincia autonoma di Trento, Piano Strategico della PAC 2023-2027](#)

capacity. This expansion brings important challenges: seasonal congestion, difficulty accessing essential services, and strong pressure on the environment, including traffic, landscape fragmentation, urban sprawl, and overexploitation of natural resources. The tourism sector accounts for more than one-third of private consumption and employs approximately 15% of the workforce, with peak flows in August. However, this significant tourism potential also impacts energy demand: the pronounced seasonality of tourist flows produces peaks in summer and winter related to accommodations, sports facilities, and transportation, alternating with sharp declines in shoulder seasons. This variability complicates energy supply management and requires innovative solutions in storage, flexibility, and planning to ensure balance and long-term sustainability.

Energy communities

The following section explores ECs currently active or emerging in Trentino - Alto Adige, a region with a very large number of cooperatives; in Alto Adige alone, there are about 823 cooperatives. This extensive cooperative network could play a key role in supporting the establishment of ECs.

Italy defines seven possible configurations for distributed self-consumption and ECs, but at present, only three are designed for sharing renewable energy and are therefore subsidised with public funds:

1. Renewable Energy Communities (CER)

This configuration enables the virtual sharing of electricity produced from renewable sources among community members. Energy is shared via the national distribution grid among producers and consumers connected to the same primary substation.

2. Collective Self-Consumption Groups (AAC)

This model involves at least two separate entities—either end-users or producers—each with its own connection point. All participants must be located within the same building or condominium. Generation systems may be installed either in the same building or in other facilities under the full control of the users, as long as they are within the same primary substation area.

3. Individual Remote Self-Consumers Using the Distribution Grid (AAD)

This configuration applies to a single end-user who virtually consumes renewable electricity generated by systems located in areas they fully control.

Energy is accessed via that user's withdrawal points connected to the public distribution grid. Table 1 shows an overview of energy configurations as of September 2025, in Trentino - Alto Adige and officially recognized by the GSE⁷.

⁷ [The GSE \(Gestore dei Servizi Energetici\) is the Italian Energy Services Operator, responsible for promoting sustainable energy production and energy efficiency.](#)

Table 1: Overview of Energy Community configurations in Trentino - Alto Adige recognized by GSE

ID	Configuration	Installed capacity (kWp)	RES systems	Members	Municipality
1	CER Green Ec Consorzio	8.98	1	2	Bressanone (BZ)
2	CER ISARCUS	11.74	2	3	Bressanone (BZ)
3	CER Valle Tures e Aurina	19.55	1	2	Campo Tures (BZ)
4	CER Sonnengemeinschaft	14.04	2	2	Parcines (BZ)
5	CER San Genesioplus	6	1	6	San Genesio Atesino (BZ)
6	CER Sarentino	58	3	61	Sarentino (BZ)
7	CER Valle Tures e Aurina	300	2	19	Valle Aurina (BZ)
8	AAD	84.55	1	1	Bressanone (BZ)
9	AAD	1146.27	4	6	Vipiteno (BZ)
10	AAC	19.5	1	8	Merano (BZ)
11	AAC	19.64	1	15	Brunico (BZ)
12	AAC	20	1	7	Lagundo (BZ)
13	AAC	28.81	6	12	Merano (BZ)
14	AAC	19.98	1	7	Brunico (BZ)
15	AAC	17.22	1	7	Lana (BZ)
16	AAC	19.92	1	2	Bressanone (BZ)
17	CER La Buona Fonte	18.56	1	25	Storo (TN)
18	CER A Doltra	8	2	3	Mezzano (TN)
19	CER Zarga	64.4	1	2	Lavis (TN)
20	CER Greenland	80	1	106	Lavarone (TN)
21	CER Koncert	634	6	81	Mezzocorona (TN)
22	CER Eyco	3	1	2	Nogaredo (TN)
23	AAD	137.38	2	22	Primiero San Martino di Castrozza (TN)
24	AAD	100	1	1	Scurelle (TN)
25	AAC	17.16	1	4	San Lorenzo Dorsino (TN)
26	AAC	6.75	1	3	Pergine Valsugana (TN)
27	AAC	19.36	1	8	Storo (TN)
28	AAC	9	1	4	Ville di Fiemme (TN)
29	AAC	4.56	1	2	Cavalese (TN)
30	AAC	6.56	1	3	Carisolo (TN)
31	AAC	9	1	5	Folgaria (TN)
32	AAC	9.9	1	13	Folgaria (TN)
33	AAC	9.9	1	5	Molveno (TN)
34	AAC	100	1	1	Storo (TN)
35	AAC	6	1	4	Novella (TN)
36	AAC	19.9	1	16	Trento

Figure 3 shows the localization of ECs in Trentino - Alto Adige, highlighting the municipal boundaries and Renewable Energy Communities, with the aim of identifying which municipal areas and RECs fall within the service area of the same primary substation—a crucial requirement for the establishment and operation of RECs, as energy sharing is only permitted among members connected to the same substation.

Figure 3: Map of primary substations and energy communities in the region Trentino - Alto Adige

Identification of key stakeholders

The following stakeholders have been identified in the region:

Energy Communities stakeholders:

- KönCeRT Trentino-based social cooperative formed as a Renewable Energy Community in 2023 - (<https://www.koncert.it/>)
- EVi Energie Vinschgau Venosta Alto Adige-based social cooperative formed as a Renewable Energy Community in 2024 - (<https://evi-energie.it/it/>)

- EEG Sarntal+ Non-profit cooperative Renewable Energy Community in Alto Adige enabling members to virtually share locally produced renewable electricity - <https://eeg-sarntal.com/>
- CIVE C'È Renewable Energy Community based in Trentino and founded in 2024 to promote a sustainable, accessible, and participatory energy model.
- CER del Sarca First cooperative Renewable Energy Community in Trentino, shares hydropower and solar energy among citizens and public entities, promoting collective renewable self-consumption and generating environmental, economic, and social benefits since its founding in March 2025 - <https://cerdelsarca.it/>

Social stakeholders:

- AGCI Alto Adige Südtirol It operates on cooperative, democratic, and mutual principles, supporting organizational growth, social solidarity, and development through representation, training, oversight, and technical, financial, and legal services - <https://www.agci-bz.it/>
- Agenzia per l'Energia Alto Adige – CasaClima Regional reference for the national RENOSS project, providing a one-stop-shop for ECs with training, technical and legal support, feasibility studies, funding guidance, project validation, and best practices for energy efficiency and sustainable community energy development - <https://www.agenziacasaclima.it>

Technical stakeholders:

- SEV – Federazione Energia Alto Adige It supports local renewable producers and small energy systems, promoting decentralized, community-driven energy. It represents members' interests, assists municipalities, and facilitates local initiatives such as ECs - <https://www.sev.bz.it/>
- Edyna It is South Tyrol's largest electricity distributor, managing a modern grid that connects producers and consumers and ensuring reliable, efficient, and environmentally compliant operations - <https://www.edyna.net>

Public bodies:

- Agenzia provinciale per l'ambiente e la tutela del clima Provincial agency responsible for environmental protection, climate policy, monitoring, and sustainability strategies; supports regional actions on energy transition, climate mitigation, and community-based renewable initiatives - <https://ambiente.provincia.bz.it>
- APRIE (Agenzia provinciale per le risorse idriche e l'energia) Provincial agency responsible for energy policy, resource management, and regulation; supports renewable energy projects and local energy initiatives - <http://www.energia.provincia.tn.it>

4. *Sizing of PV systems*

This section outlines the methodological approach used to size photovoltaic systems and analyze the associated energy flows.

The energy assets of the community are owned by the individual members who install them. Energy is first used to meet each owner's self-consumption, with any surplus shared across the community. However, the sizing of these installations is optimized for the EC as a whole, not for individual users, so while some systems may exceed a single owner's needs, they are efficient and balanced within the broader community context.

The analysis relies on a RECTool⁸, a model designed by EURAC for ECs and adapted to the Italian context, which adopts a bottom-up structure and uses linear programming techniques, with a one-year time horizon and a static framework.

The RECTool is employed to perform a techno-economic-environmental assessment of the REC and to optimize its configuration, providing estimates of the system's energy, economic, and environmental impacts. The model is implemented through oemof⁹, which allows constraints and objective functions to be expressed as linear formulations solved through linear programming.

The analysis has two main objectives:

- optimizing, by considering also economies of scale, the installed capacity of photovoltaic systems (subject to maximum installable limits, where applicable) and battery storage;
- optimizing the dispatch of energy resources within the REC, while minimizing the costs.

The cost components considered include capital and operational expenditures (CAPEX and OPEX), energy-related costs (electricity bills, incentives, revenues from energy sold to the grid), and any tax deductions or similar benefits.

To clarify the energy-cost structure represented in the model, a definition of shared energy is needed: shared electricity is calculated hourly for all connection points linked to the same primary substation and is defined as the minimum between the electricity injected and the electricity withdrawn for sharing purposes.

The following section provides a brief overview of the incentives and cost components relevant to ECs as there are the following support mechanisms designed to promote their development:

⁸ [Casalicchio, V., Manzolini, G., Prina, M. G., & Moser, D. \(2022\). From investment optimization to fair benefit distribution in renewable energy community modelling. Applied Energy, 310, 118447. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118447](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118447)

⁹ [oemof \(Open Energy Modelling Framework\) is an open-source Python-based framework designed for the modelling and optimisation of energy systems.](#)

- compensation for shared electricity, provided through the reimbursement of specific tariff components (ARERA Resolution 727/2022/R/eel¹⁰).
- premium tariff for shared electricity, established by the CACER Decree¹¹. This tariff consists of a fixed component, linked to the size of the installation, and a variable component that depends on the market price of electricity. An additional premium is applied to photovoltaic systems located in Central Italy and Northern Italy to compensate for their lower productivity compared to installations in Southern Italy. The premium is granted by the GSE for 20 years from the commissioning date of each renewable energy plant. A 50% tax deduction for building renovations¹² can be combined with capital grants.
- compensation for the electricity withdrawal into the grid provided by the GSE¹³.

5. *Financial model*

The financing of a REC can be structured in different ways, depending on its ownership model and the type of partners involved.

Energy plants may be directly owned by the CER, allowing the community to manage production and revenues autonomously, or they may be owned by third parties - either public or private entities - that make the generated energy available for sharing within the community.

For a small-to-medium scale REC in Italy, the most realistic and sustainable financing structure combines private investments by individual members with tax incentives (50% tax deduction available to eligible residential prosumers).

This financial model is proposed in combination with revenues from shared electricity, including the premium tariff for shared energy and compensation for electricity injected into the grid, ensuring both economic viability and member participation.

6. *Business plan*

The business plan has been drawn up to ensure the long-term financial sustainability and viability of the REC and follows key parameters, including revenue sources, investment costs, operating expenses, and financial and fiscal charges.

The REC applies annual membership fees to its participants to cover administrative, technical, and operational costs. A fixed membership fee of €25 per year is charged to

¹⁰ [Delibera 727/2022/R/EEL dell'Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente](#)

¹¹ [Decreto del Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica del 7 dicembre 2023, n. 414](#)

¹² [Article 16-bis of Presidential Decree 917/1986, letter h](#)

¹³ [Decreto Legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 199](#)

consumers. For prosumers and producers, the annual membership fee ranges from €50 to €500, depending on the installed PV system size.

Table 2: Savings and incomes input data deployed in the Business Plan

Savings / incomes	Unit	Value
Remuneration for the electricity injected into the grid	€/kWh	≈ 0.096
Savings from physical self-consumption	€/kWh	≈ 0.24
Premium tariff for shared energy	€/kWh	≈ 0.123
Compensation of tariff components	€/kWh	≈ 0.011

Table 3: Investment and costs input data deployed in the Business Plan

Investments / costs	Unit	Value
Investment for plant construction	€/kWp	≈ 1100 – 1600 *
Operation and maintenance costs	€/kWp/year	≈ 15 – 20 *
Platform management costs	€/year	2500
Administrative management costs	€/year	6500
Other operating costs	€/year	15000
* For PV systems with a capacity ranging from 6 to 150 kWp		

The REC analysed in this study spans three distinct primary substations. Consequently, each substation corresponds to a separate energy configuration, and the portion of shared energy eligible for incentives must be calculated individually for each configuration.

Overall, the community consists of 128 consumers and 12 producers, distributed across the three configurations as follows:

- configuration 1: cabin A - 58 connection points (5 prosumers, 53 consumers), including public offices, commercial and industrial facilities, educational buildings, and residential units.

- configuration 2: cabin B - 48 connection points (5 prosumers, 43 consumers), including an alpine hut, school, kindergarten, bank, museum, retail, production facilities, and residential units.
- configuration 3: cabin C - 34 connection points (2 prosumers, 32 consumers), including a warehouse, parking, small industrial production, cafeteria, retail, supermarket, office, and residential units.

Cabin	Type	Consumption (kWh/year)	Category	Max capacity (kWp)
A	Municipal Office	907,132	prosumer	80
	SME	592,128	prosumer	130
	School	163,302	prosumer	150
	Supermarket	155,999	consumer	-
	Retail Store	34,399	consumer	-
	Parking	36,000	consumer	-
	Church	1,999	consumer	-
	Winery production	300,000	consumer	-
	Winery production	300,000	consumer	-
	Kindergarten	93,509	consumer	-
	2 residential households	7,138	prosumers	6
46 residential households	165,839	consumers	-	
B	Alpine Hut	8,222	prosumer	15
	Kindergarten	21,000	prosumer	120
	School	183,896	consumer	20
	Gym	120,000	consumer	-
	Retail Store	34,399	consumer	-
	SME	13,500	consumer	-
	Winery production	300,000	consumer	-
	Museum	31,500	consumer	-
	2 residential households	7,061	prosumers	6
	38 residential households	138,778	consumers	-
C	Warehouse	40,570	prosumer	80
	Parking	36,000	producer	150
	Small production enterprise	300,000	consumer	-
	Cafeteria	15,750	consumer	-
	Retail Store	34,399	consumer	-
	Supermarket	155,999	consumer	-
	Office	13,500	consumer	-
	27 residential households	97,586	consumers	-

The following section introduces the optimization results for each configuration, highlighting energy flows, economic benefits, and environmental impacts. Data are shown in three different categories:

1. technical data, such as installed PV capacity, energy production, consumption and self-consumption, grid feed-in, shared energy;
2. economic data, such as investment cost, savings from energy self-consumption, incentives, revenue, O&M costs;

3. identified KPIs, such as share of Self-consumption, Self-sufficiency, CO₂ avoided, NPV over 25 years, Internal Rate of Return, payback period.

Table 4: Technical data of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)	Configuration 3 (Cabin C)
Installed PV capacity	kWp	372	167	169
Estimated annual production	MWh/year	503,604	218,921	209,986
Aggregated consumption	kWh/year	2,757,447	858,358	693,805
Self-consumption	kWh/year	336,519	43,592	30,959
Energy fed into the grid	kWh/year	167,086	175,328	179,026
of which shared energy	%	100	99	93

Table 5: Economic data of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)	Configuration 3 (Cabin C)
Initial investment	€	420,378	197,855	192,174
Bill savings	€/year	80,018	10,415	7,397
Incentive for shared energy	€/year	38,148	39,551	37,860
Energy sold to the grid	€/year	0	177	1,220
Operation & Maintenance	€/year	7,380	3,280	3,381
Annual operating costs (platform + administrative costs)	€/year	24,000		

Table 6: Identified KPIs of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)	Configuration 3 (Cabin C)
Self consumption (physical+virtual)	%	98		
Self sufficiency	%	21		
CO ₂ avoided	t/year	109	47	43
NPV - 25 years (with bonus 50%)	€	987,920	303,740	259,555
IRR	%	15		
Payback period	year	6		

Notes on the results:

- battery storage was excluded by the optimization due to its high investment costs.
- the three system configurations were optimized under a constraint on the maximum installable PV capacity. While the first two configurations fully exploit the maximum allowable capacity, the third configuration does not reach this upper limit.
- for residential users, the 50% tax deduction on eligible investments is applied. This deduction reduces income taxes over ten years and is therefore incorporated in the calculation of NPV for these users.
- annual operating costs are allocated among the configurations proportionally to the share of incentivized energy, although other allocation methods could be used. For the first year, the initial operating cost is considered 15% higher than in subsequent years to account for startup expenses.
- starting from the 21st year, incentives for shared energy are no longer provided, in accordance with current regulations.
- as incentivized energy exceeds 55% of total energy fed into the grid, proceeds go to non-business members or are reinvested for local social purposes.

7. *Legal aspects*

RECs are often initially constituted as associations, with the intention of subsequently obtaining legal personality or converting into a cooperative as the community expands, both in terms of membership and number of energy installations.

The most selected configuration for the REC is a non-profit cooperative, as it ensures democratic governance, clear separation of assets, fiscal benefits, and the possibility of distributing economic benefits to members, making it particularly suitable for larger RECs aiming for structured management and benefit sharing.

The REC may include a variety of members, such as natural persons, as well as public and local bodies. Small and medium-sized enterprises (including those partially owned by public authorities) may join only if their main business activity is not the production or sale of energy, while large enterprises are not eligible to become members.

Other eligible participants include associations, foundations, religious organizations, Third Sector Entities (ETS), consortia, and research or training institutions.

The management structure consists of:

1. *Assemblea dei Soci (General Assembly)* – the sovereign body of the cooperative.

It approves the financial statements, appoints and revokes the members of the Board of Directors and the Auditors, determines their remuneration, and approves internal regulations and statutory amendments.

2. Consiglio di Amministrazione (Board of Directors) – composed of 3 to 9 members, it oversees both the ordinary and extraordinary management of the cooperative. It prepares operational plans and development strategies, defines the economic and financial policies, and may delegate specific functions to one or more directors.

The President of the Consiglio di Amministrazione legally represents the cooperative.

3. Collegio Sindacale (Board of Statutory Auditors) – elected by the Assemblea dei Soci, it ensures compliance with the law and the bylaws, supervises management, and certifies the accuracy of the social report. The task of statutory auditing (revisione legale dei conti) may be assigned either to the Collegio or to an external auditor.

The establishment and ongoing management of the REC require the following documentation:

1. Atto costitutivo (Deed of Incorporation) – specifying the founding members;
2. Statuto (By-laws) – defining the internal governance structure and voting rights;
3. Regole di ripartizione (Benefit distribution rules) – establishing the criteria for the allocation of incentives among members;
4. Contratto tariffa premio GSE (GSE Premium - Tariff Agreement) – to be executed within 90 days from the commissioning of the installations;
5. Contratto di vendita dell'energia (Energy Sale Agreement) – governing the injection of produced energy into the public grid;
6. Contratti di servizio (Service Agreements) – covering production, maintenance, administrative and IT management of the REC.

Any party wishing to be admitted as a member must submit a written application to the Board of Directors, containing the following information:

If the applicant is a natural person:

1. Full name, residence, date and place of birth, contact number, Italian Tax Identification Number, and certified e-mail;
2. Identification codes and point of delivery, indicating their location and specifying whether the applicant is a consumer or prosumer;
3. Details of the production plants or portions thereof whose energy injected into the grid (and not self-consumed) contributes to the REC's shared energy calculation, if the applicant is a producer or prosumer;

4. A copy of the most recent electricity bill for estimating annual consumption (if not otherwise accessible through institutional channels);
5. The amount of capital proposed for subscription, within the by-laws limits;
6. A declaration of full knowledge and acceptance of the current by-laws, internal regulations, and resolutions legally adopted by the corporate bodies;
7. An express and separate declaration of acceptance of the arbitration clause contained in the Statuto and confirmation of having examined the rules of the Camera Arbitrale e di Conciliazione della Cooperazione¹⁴.

If the applicant is a company, association, or other entity:

1. Legal name or denomination, legal form, registered office, contact number, Tax Identification Number, VAT number, and certified e-mail address;
2. For enterprises, the prevalent *codice ATECO* of their economic activity and a declaration stating that participation in the Cooperative as an EC does not constitute their principal commercial or industrial activity;
3. The resolution of the competent corporate body authorizing the application;
4. Identification of the signatory and their legal authority to represent the applicant;
5. For enterprises, a declaration attesting to their qualification as an SME.

8. *Methodology for engagement*

The REC of the Calatayud Region (CERCA), developed within the framework of the European JALON project, has carried out a series of citizen engagement activities targeting residents, associations, and local administrations. Through meetings with residents of various municipalities and training workshops, CERCA has presented the benefits of sustainable energy and provided technical, economic, and legal information on ECs. Additional training days have been planned to extend engagement to associations, private individuals, and businesses.

Given the success of this methodology and considering that Italian experiences in the region have also organized similar public training sessions to engage the community, it is suggested that the same approach based on JALON's results be adopted for replication in Trentino - Alto Adige. By combining informative workshops, direct community involvement, and tailored outreach strategies, this approach has proven effective in raising awareness, fostering participation, and ensuring that ECs are integrated successfully into local social and economic contexts.

Since the region already hosts active and successful configurations, engagement activities could be further strengthened by demonstrating the feasibility of local energy

¹⁴ Body providing alternative dispute resolution services (arbitration and conciliation) for cooperatives.

systems through showcasing real, operational examples, such as existing shared photovoltaic installations and already-implemented community energy projects.

9. Conclusions

The REC in Trentino - Alto Adige proposed in this design is summarised below:

- Size of the REC (number of participants), of which:
 - Primary cabins: 3
 - Citizens: 115 households
 - Local shops / commercial 9
 - Industries / production 7
 - Local councils / public services 8

- Type and number of self-consumption PV systems:
 - Residential collective systems: 4 PV installations without storage, with an average power of 6 kWp (total power of 24 kWp).
 - Local shops and commercial buildings collective systems: 2 PV installations without storage, with a total power of 165 kWp.
 - Industrial and production PV systems: 2 PV installations without storage, with a total power of 210 kWp.
 - Local councils and public services PV systems: 4 PV installations without storage, with a total power of 370 kWp.

Total: **12 PV installations** without storage, with a total power of **708 kWp**.

The 12 installations produce **933 MWh** of energy annually.

- Needed investment and funding for:
 - Phase 1: REC set-up (Year 0):
 - Platform, administrative, other operating costs. Non-repayable public funding. **€27,600**.
 - Phase 2: Development of PV projects (Years 1–25):
 - 100% from investments of participant prosumers **€810,407**
 - Platform, administrative, other operating costs. Non-repayable public funding. **€24,000**.
 - The 50% tax deduction (Art. 16-bis DPR 917/1986¹²) allows residential prosumers/producers to offset half of eligible renovation costs against income tax over 10 years. **€19,320**
 - compensation for shared electricity, (ARERA Resolution 727/2022/R/eel¹⁰) + premium tariff for shared electricity (CACER Decree¹¹) + compensation for the electricity injected **€116,956**

- REC structure:
 - Legal: non-profit cooperative
 - Electricity suppliers (free choice)

- Resources:
 - Staff: 2/4 volunteers (free-time),
 - PV system maintenance service.
 - administrator/financial service
- Business plan:
 - The REC charges fees to project participants:
 - REC consumer membership fee: **€25**
 - REC prosumer/producer membership fee: **€50 - €500** (according to PV size)

These figures generate a positive cash flow after 6 years. Over a period of 25 years, this represents an **IRR of 15%**, which ensures the financial sustainability of the REC.

In line with the aim of the Jalon project, an energy community with a predominantly social purpose and services linked to the local territory was examined. The REC consists of 12 photovoltaic installations distributed across residential homes, neighbourhood shops and commercial buildings, small industries and public buildings. The total installed capacity of the system thus created is 708kWp. Although designed primarily for self-consumption and without the support of storage batteries, the total energy produced by the plants and shared by the members of the REC generates an annual cash flow of approximately €117,000/year. This figure, net of fixed technical and administrative management costs (estimated at between €27,000 and €31,000/year), allows for the amortisation of the installed systems in the sixth year and a subsequent income that the REC can dedicate to social initiatives in the local area.

In fact, during the engagement phase and meetings with citizens, the REC project design consistently aligns with the CACER decree whereby the, REC revenues are designated for social purposes and the activation or enhancement of local services for citizens.

Technical and economic simulations highlighted the long-term financial sustainability of the energy community, which is a constantly evolving organism. Currently, the creation and management of the REC are only just beginning, and much work remains to be done in raising awareness and managing energy flows to ensure the economic sustainability of the community itself. The topic of contrasting the rural depopulation, of creating professional roles in the area and of establishing new neighbourhood services for community members will need to be monitored in the coming years.